

D7.4

Dissemination Plan

PoDIUM

PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM

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List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ASECAP	European Association of Operators of Toll Road Infrastructures
CAV	Connected Automated Vehicle
CBC	Cross-border corridor
CCAM	Cooperative, connected and automated mobility
CEDR	Conference of European Directors of Roads
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems
CINEA	European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency
CNERT	Computer and Networking Experimental Research using Testbeds
CTTE	Conference of Telecommunication, Media and Internet Techno-Economics
D7.4	Deliverable 7.4
DoA	Description of Actions
EC	European Commission
ERF	European Road Federation
EU	European Union
EUCAD	European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving
EuCNC	European Conference on Networks and Communications
GLOBECOM	Global Communications Conference
IBTTA	International Bridge, Tunnels and Turnpike Association
ICC	International Conference on Communications
ICCRS	International Conference on Cyber Resilience and Security (ICCRS)
ICTON	International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IFIP	International Federation for Information Processing
IRF	International Road Transport Union
IRU	International Road Federation
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems
ITSC	International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems

IV	Intelligent Vehicles
LANMAN	Local and Metropolitan Area Networks
LCN	Local Computer Networks
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MITMA	Spanish Ministry of Transport Mobility and Urban Agenda
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MWC	Mobile World Congress
NSDI	Networked Systems Design and Implementation
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
OBU	On-Board Unit
OEM	Original equipment manufacturer
PDI	Physical and Digital Infrastructure
PoDIUM	PDI connectivity and cooperation enablers building trust and sustainability for CCAM
R&D	Research & Development
RSU	Road-Side Unit
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
RTR	Results from Road Transport Research
SCEWC	Smart City Expo World Congress
SME	Small and medium-sized enterprise
TL	Task Leader
TMC	Traffic Management Centre
TNSM	Transactions on Network and Service Management
TRA	Transport Research Arena
UC	Use Case
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VNC	Vehicular Networking Conference
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
VTC	Vehicular Technology Conference
WP	Work Package

WoWMoM

World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks

Executive Summary

Deliverable 7.4 is a public deliverable and the outcome of Task 7.2, Dissemination Activities and Events, carried out as part of PoDIUM's Work Package (WP) 7 on 'Dissemination, exploitation, and international cooperation'. D7.4 Dissemination Plan provides initial dissemination targets and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), as well as an initial list of events to carry out the dissemination activities. It clearly defines the dissemination strategy and the plan of action that will be implemented by PoDIUM's partners to ensure that the project and its results are effectively disseminated throughout the project's lifecycle. It identifies the topics of interest of each of the project's target audiences, describes the means and channels that will be employed and serves as a reference point for the dissemination activities planned and the role undertaken by the project partners. Moreover, it sets the success criteria for the evaluation of the dissemination activities performed per year. Complementary, the deliverable includes the procedures to be followed for dissemination activities carried out by consortium partners.

The main objectives of the dissemination plan are to raise awareness, disseminate PoDIUM's activities, progress and results to expert communities, ensure a good scientific reputation for the project and increase its outreach and impact, through the participation of partners at relevant conferences and events, the production and publication of scientific and technical papers and the organization of the project's demonstration events. During the entire duration of the project, partners will act as key players, actively participating in dissemination activities to inform target groups about:

- CCAM systems and services enabling connectivity and cooperation;
- Europe's activities (such as previous projects) and funding efforts to advance CCAM;
- The extension of TMC to MEC and overall, the use of MEC to host CCAM services;
- The potentials of advanced perception modelling and digital twins in CCAM services;
- Methods to ensure software integrity and data truthfulness;
- Schemes to better integrate vehicles and VRUs in traffic management.

The consortium will use online and social media, print media (technical and general), events, conferences, and exhibitions to increase the visibility of the project and progresses. Partners will participate in several industry events: conferences, congresses, workshops, and other external events to disseminate the project's progress and its results, as well as to receive feedback from experts and relevant stakeholders. Special efforts will be made for participating in the annual ITS World and European Congresses and EUCNCs. Moreover, PoDIUM will publish its activities and results in scientific peer-reviewed journals and conference proceedings to broadcast its results and get feedback from the scientific and professional community. Webinars addressing different topics and categories of stakeholders will be organised at regular intervals to provide a comprehensive overview of particular results of the project, while PoDIUM will produce videos introducing the project and the Living Lab demonstrations. To maximise the project impact, increase synergies and avoid overlaps, PoDIUM will coordinate with past and future R&D projects and liaison with already established networks, associations, organisations as well as related fora and technical communities to exchange knowledge and views in common research fields, present technical advances and organise joint dissemination activities.

Finally, the project will organize 4 events, including 3 major demonstration events at the three different Living Labs (LLs) i.e. in Germany, Spain and Italy, to demonstrate the PoDIUM Use Cases (UCs) in real traffic conditions, as well as the final project event helping to present the vision and strategy of CCAM partnership, and to efficiently showcase the project progress to multiple stakeholders.

Throughout the lifecycle of the project, all consortium members will participate in the activities of WP7 and the dissemination of PoDIUM results to ensure that the objectives of the dissemination strategy and the targets of the dissemination plan are being met. Details of planned and performed dissemination activities will be saved on the project's shared documents and advertised on the project's website: <https://podium-project.eu/>.

1. Introduction

1.1. Project introduction

PoDIUM aims to support advanced use cases of connected and cooperative automated mobility in actual traffic conditions. Building urban and highway UCs on the facilities of 3 well-equipped Living Labs in Germany, Italy, and Spain, PoDIUM will tackle all the different requirements for the availability and performance of connectivity as well as the different cooperation enablers per UC. The proposed UCs aim to advance a set of key technologies both in the physical and digital parts of the infrastructure. In particular, the following non-exhaustive list of contributions will be pursued:

- A multi-connectivity approach to ensure reliability, availability and redundancy of the Physical and Digital Infrastructure (PDI) system.
- Advance data fusion and integration of Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) to the proposed hybrid data management environment to enable enhanced environment perception models towards digital twins.
- New Cooperative Intelligent Transport Systems (C-ITS) messages for enabling the specific advanced Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) use cases.
- Ensure software integrity, trust and truthfulness of CCAM data, their exchange and their processing.
- Demonstration of urban and highway use cases in a diverse set of configurations with the integration of Vulnerable Road Users (VRU).

1.2. WP7 – Dissemination, Exploitation and International Cooperation

PoDIUM's WP7 includes activities that happen horizontally and in conjunction with the other project work packages. The aim is to bring high visibility to PoDIUM activities and outcomes by ensuring a strong presence at relevant events and through online channels and social media. The WP7 team in collaboration with consortium members will also foster the dissemination of the PoDIUM results by involving and engaging relevant stakeholders in fora and consultation workshops to ensure the widest diffusion of the project's outcomes, helping to achieve the vision and strategy of the CCAM partnership.

In particular, the main objectives of WP7 are:

- Develop a **Communication and Dissemination strategy and plan** for soundly promoting the progress and outputs of PoDIUM and streamlining wide awareness;
- Develop the necessary **brand identity and communication materials and tools** for targeted promotion, so as to ensure mainstreaming of the project's results to a wide range of stakeholders at all geographical levels and relevant sectors;
- Coordinate the **scientific outreach** through the development of open access papers and participation in scientific and industrial events;
- **Liaise with relevant R&D projects, already established organisations/associations and networks, standardisation bodies** to ensure knowledge exchange, interoperability of the developed systems as well as wide market penetration;

- Develop the necessary methodology and assist partners in the preparation of **homogeneous and effective exploitation plans** for PoDIUM;
- Contribute, upon invitation by the CINEA, to common information and dissemination activities to **increase the visibility and synergies between HE/H2020 supported actions**.

The WP7 for ‘Dissemination, Exploitation and International Cooperation’ consists of four tasks (as foreseen in the DoA), and each one is led by a project partner i.e. the Task Leader (TL), who will be supported by one or more partners involved in WP7 or with resources in that particular task, and 11 deliverables ([Annex 3](#)). All WP7 tasks are interrelated and complementary, thus they are aligned under the supervision of the WP7 Leader, ERTICO. In [Annex 2](#), the WP7 tasks, their leaders, and their description are outlined.

1.3. Deliverable 7.4 – Dissemination plan

The purpose of **D7.4 Dissemination Plan** is to outline the project’s dissemination strategy and plan and to act as a reference point for the WP7 team and partners by providing a detailed description of the opportunities and activities connected with WP7 and Task 7.2 – *Dissemination Activities and Events* in particular. The document provides an overview of dissemination objectives, methods, and tools, planned dissemination activities, internal reporting procedures, dissemination performance metrics (KPIs), and liaison with relevant projects and initiatives.

Chapter one of the deliverable starts with an introduction to PoDIUM, the role of WP7 in the project, and the purpose and structure of the document. **Chapter two** develops the dissemination strategy, means and road map, as well as the topics of interest per target audience. Additionally, the procedure for assessing the dissemination activities is presented. **Chapter three** describes how this strategy will be implemented and presents detailed information about targeted events, conferences, journals, the topics that each partner will be covering and an overview of the project’s main demonstration events, planned webinars and videos, and liaison opportunities to enhance dissemination efforts. The conclusion forms the **last chapter**. The deliverable also includes a set of annexes, where the dissemination approval procedures, WP7 tasks and leaders, WP7 partner participation, and a list of the WP7 deliverables are presented.

The deliverable is a dynamic document and will therefore be regularly evaluated and updated to ensure its alignment with the progress of the overall project activities and potential external changes.

1.3.1. Intended audience

This deliverable is public (PU dissemination level) and it is intended for:

- Members of the PoDIUM consortium** – to find all the information they need concerning the project’s dissemination plan, tools, and procedures;
- The European Commission** (as a funding authority) – to get an overview of the dissemination of planned activities and targets and to assess the quality of the document;
- Anyone interested** in getting more information about the PoDIUM project e.g. relevant stakeholders, other projects and initiatives, external partners, etc. – to access information on the project’s dissemination plan, channels, and activities.

1.3.2. Relation of D7.4 to other WP7 deliverables

Communication and Dissemination are integral parts of a project and crucial for its success and long-lasting effect. Therefore, respective strategies and plans should be established at the early stages of the project to lead project partners through the process and strengthen engagement in WP7 activities.

Three separate documents have been created as foreseen in the DoA:

- a) D7.2 Communication strategy and plan [1],
- b) D7.3 Communication tools [2], and
- c) D7.4 Dissemination plan.

The aforementioned documents are interrelated, but not overlapping. More specifically, **D7.2 Communication strategy and plan** focuses on the communication activities that will maximise the project's public awareness and visibility and defines the overall strategy and plan for communication, dissemination, and liaison activities. Then, **D7.3 Communication tools** describes the development and the available communication tools to be used for promoting PoDIUM. Finally, the **D7.4 Dissemination plan** provides an initial dissemination strategy and sets the KPIs, describes the channels and tools to be deployed, and provides an initial list of the planned activities to disseminate the project's results and outcomes.

2. Dissemination objectives and strategy

The dissemination strategy has been developed to ensure that the PoDIUM results are systematically disseminated to the expert communities and relevant stakeholders throughout the lifetime of the project. The main objectives are to raise awareness, disseminate PoDIUM’s activities, progress and results to expert communities, ensure a good scientific reputation for the project and increase its outreach, and impact. The focus of the dissemination strategy will be on the following activities:

- Organising the presentation of PoDIUM activities and results in conferences and other events, dedicated to PoDIUM special sessions, oral and poster presentations, and workshops;
- Ensuring the production and publication of scientific and technical papers from the PoDIUM experts in conference proceedings and top-ranked peer-reviewed scientific and technology journals;
- Organising demonstration events and press conferences, for each PoDIUM demonstration activity and during some targeted conferences and trade fairs.

PoDIUM’s dissemination strategy aims to reach the broadest possible target stakeholder groups and to be effective and efficient, the dissemination plan needs to:

- a) be oriented towards the needs of the specific audience, using appropriate key messages;
- b) use various dissemination means and channels;
- c) leverage existing resources, relationships, and networks of partners;
- d) set ambitious, yet attainable goals to motivate partners;

This section includes the main aspects of PoDIUM’s dissemination strategy, including the key messages and topics of interest, as well as the stakeholders to whom the external dissemination actions will be addressed (2.1) the dissemination means and channels (2.2) that will be used by the consortium to diffuse the project’s key messages and findings, the dissemination roadmap to align efforts with the project’s technical progress (2.3) and finally, the six dissemination indicators (2.4) for measuring the project’s dissemination performance.

2.1. Target audience and topics of interest

During the entire duration of the project, partners will act as key players, actively participating in dissemination activities to inform target groups about:

- CCAM systems and services enabling connectivity and cooperation;
- Europe’s activities (such as previous projects) and funding efforts to advance CCAM;
- The extension of TMC to MEC and overall, the use of MEC to host CCAM services;
- The potentials of advanced perception modelling and digital twins in CCAM services;
- Methods to ensure software integrity and data truthfulness;
- Schemes to better integrate vehicles and VRUs in traffic management.

The identification and detailed definition of relevant actors and targeted communities are critical for disseminating information and results in a targeted and effective manner. A detailed presentation of PoDIUM’s target groups and main key messages is available in Section 3.2, ‘D7.2 Communication

strategy and plan’, while the topics of interest per target group identified for PoDIUM’s dissemination activities are the following:

Table 1: PoDIUM dissemination target groups and topics of interest

Target Group	Topic(s) of Interest
Industries (for business exploitation): Including sectors involved in the project (ICT & software suppliers; infrastructure suppliers; telecommunication operators, information providers, OEMs, road operators, TMC operators, etc.).	
OEMs-MNOs-Telecom Vendors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CCAM services and multi-connectivity approach. • Use of 5G mmWave in CCAM services along with higher penetration and use of MEC-based CCAM services. • C-ITS services providing connectivity to CAVs, VRUs, and conventional vehicles. • New data generation and sharing strategies; improved capabilities and new mobility functionalities for CAVs.
Tier-1 suppliers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel driving functions with CCAM Services. • MEC use, multi-connectivity, new traffic management schemes including data from vehicles, and VRUs, etc.
Road, TMC operators, public entities, and CCAM service providers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New traffic management processes, advancement of traffic safety measures and emergency services, design of data interfaces to CAVs and VRUs and their benefits from potential investment into the digital road infrastructure. • Higher integration of vehicles and VRUs and their produced data in the traffic management process. • Enhanced Digital Twins combining static road attributes and real-time dynamic information.
Institutions (for implementation and follow-up/take-up aspects) including but not limited to: policy and decision-makers at European and national levels; standardisation bodies; national or regional funding bodies, etc	
European Commission / CINEA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Acceleration of the deployment of advanced CCAM services in Europe. • EU leadership in innovation related to CCAM Services. • Sustainability and market potential of PoDIUM’s advanced functionalities. • Recommendations for the adoption of the CCAM technologies developed in the project, in European transport infrastructures.
International and National projects and initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • PoDIUM reference architecture. • Multipath communication schemes. • Large-scale demonstration of 5 UCs in real traffic conditions and in urban and highway setups. • New software integrity and data truthfulness methods. • Cost-benefit analysis of CCAM services for all actors involved.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Methods, business models, guideline and recommendations for advanced CCAM services. • Dissemination and Communication Activities.
Standardization WGs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovation processes. • Methods, business models, guideline and recommendations for advanced CCAM services. • Implementation of national and European guidelines.
CCAM partnership, C-ITS Platform, EUCAR & other associations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data management from different sources, interoperability and better coordination between actors. • Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) development for the next work programmes based on the PoDIUM findings
<p>Scientific and research community (for cross-fertilization and transfer of results to follow-up initiatives) including but not limited to: academic and research centres; operators of test sites to integrate piloted technologies for future applications, etc.</p>	
RTOs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advances in autonomous driving and V2X technologies, in the corresponding PDI technical working items. • Use of 5G mmWave in CCAM services combined with LTE/5G. • C-ITS message validation and deployment activities (e.g., C-ROADS) extensions of key messages with quality indicators will benefit the future data fusion mechanisms. • New software integrity and trust and data truthfulness methods.
<p>Users (for acceptance, usability and impact assessment) including but not limited to: sector organisations representing industry end-users; user groups impacted by developed technologies; end-user associations, etc.</p>	
CAV & Conventional vehicle users, VRUs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participation in the overall traffic management schemes by data sharing.
Media & General Public	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Large scale demonstration of 5 UCs is real traffic conditions and in urban and highway setups. • Improvement of EU road users' everyday lives. • Real-time notifications about emergency cases. • Improved traffic flow and reduced traffic volume. • Reduced emissions and adoption of MaaS transportation systems, especially in rural areas close to cross-border highways.

2.2. Dissemination means and channels

The consortium will use a variety of channels to put PoDIUM in the spotlight and to start a dialogue with its diverse target audiences. Depending on the nature of the message and the stakeholder group for whom it is intended, the consortium will use online and social media, print media (technical and general), events, conferences, and exhibitions to increase the visibility of the project and progresses. PoDIUM partners will employ the following means to effectively disseminate the project's developments and results:

- **Scientific and technical papers:** Papers in conference proceedings and journals, technical reports, white papers, etc.; (see 3.2.2)
- **Presentations in conferences and external events:** Oral and poster presentations, special sessions, panel discussions, webinars, and workshops; (3.2.1)
- **Trade shows and exhibitions:** fairs and exhibitions around Europe and globally, to present the project's progress and also to get in touch with potential future customers;
- **Project events:** the project will organise 4 events, including 3 demonstration events (one at each involved LL) as well as the final project event; (see 3.1.1)
- **PoDIUM webinars:** webinars will be organised by the PoDIUM consortium or jointly with other projects to reach people who have a stated interest in the project's work and engage relevant stakeholders; (see 3.3)
- **Videos:** related to the overall project, the demonstrations, as well as the project's developments and activities; (see 3.4)
- **PoDIUM website:** the [PoDIUM website](#) will include blog posts written by partners, public deliverables, publications (pre-prints or openly accessible publications), presentations, project activities such as organization of PoDIUM events/webinars, links from the established dissemination synergies with similar projects and initiatives as well as news from any performed joint activities with them.
- **PoDIUM social media:** Within the context of promoting the project results widely and effectively, the project's social media accounts on [LinkedIn](#) and [Twitter](#) will also be utilised with constant updates about publications, events, presentations and other dissemination activities performed by the consortium.
- **Zenodo:** The scope of the [PoDIUM Zenodo community](#) is to make all public deliverables, scientific publications, and public results of the project freely available and under open access status.
- **ERTICO Academy:** An ad-hoc knowledge base training programme to support and foster sustainable deployment of ITS and C-ITS across Europe among Public Authority officials across Europe.
- **HEU networking activities:** Results and other information and ideas will be shared with related HEU projects and other relevant actors from the ongoing CCAM Partnership (and not only) projects. Workshops or other activities/events will be sought wherever relevant and mutually beneficial.
- **Press and online media:** To increase the visibility and potential impact of PoDIUM results the Consortium led by the WP7 leader, will approach local and international media, including newspapers, magazines, and online sources such as blogs. The consortium will liaise with individual journalists specializing in the PoDIUM technology areas in order to inform and engage stakeholders about the project.
- **Consortium and project partners:** All partners in the consortium will disseminate project results internally in their organisations (and in their contacts). The academic project partners will disseminate the project vision and results to staff and students.

2.3. Dissemination Roadmap

During the first months (M01-M09), the activities start with assessing the specifications and requirements of the main building blocks of the project, and therefore, the aim of the dissemination

activities is to generally **inform target stakeholders about the project’s main objectives and expected outcomes and results**. In this first phase, the project has already been introduced in the [2nd CCAM Multicluster meeting](#) (25 October 2023, Brussels), during the “Meet Horizon Europe projects” session at the European Commission’s stand of the [RTR Conference](#) (14-16 February 2023, Brussels) and to CINEA's new brochure on CCAM (soon to be available). The consortium has also been involved in proposals to participate in workshops and special sessions at conferences, such as ITS Europe, INFOCOM, and ITS World Congress, while an invited paper presentation is anticipated (M08) at the International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON). PoDIUM will also participate at the 4th European Conference on Connected and Automated Driving - [EUCAD 2023](#) (3 May 2023, Brussels) with the co-organisation of a breakout session and an exhibition stand during the EUCAD/EUCAR Networking Event, next to other EU-funded PDI and CCAM projects. Additionally, the project’s social media were created (M03) and the official website was launched (M05) to introduce PoDIUM to relevant stakeholders and promote its dissemination activities. Finally, [a press release](#) has been issued in M05 to announce the kick-off meeting and the launch of the project activities, and the project’s informative flyer and poster have been designed (M06) to be widely disseminated online and at events (see D7.3 Communication Tools).

As we move on towards the second phase of the project (M09-M24), partners will be regularly encouraged to disseminate **initial results and developments** through technical papers, workshops, webinars, presentations, liaison activities with similar projects, etc.

In the final phase of the project (M25 – M36), a major effort will be made in the **organisation of the demonstration events** and in effectively **disseminating the project’s results** to the **key audiences** to ensure the fostering of future sustainability. Particularly, technical papers presenting the final results of PoDIUM will be published at various scientific conferences and journals, while demonstrations of the available solutions will be showcased at relevant events and exhibitions. The PoDIUM consortium will also organise or participate in presentations at workshops, sessions, and webinars, concerning the “go to market” strategy and proposed actions towards EU utilization of connectivity and cooperation enablers in the future CCAM services. A strong effort will also be given to press releases and media involvement, to engage end-users and the general public and inform them about the benefits of CCAM solutions in their everyday life.

2.4. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The performed dissemination activities throughout the project’s lifecycle will be monitored through a set dissemination procedure ([Annex 1](#)) and will be constantly discussed and evaluated amongst the consortium. Although it is difficult to assess the true impact of the project’s dissemination activities, quantitative indicators present some measurable values to help evaluate the degree to which the targets are met. Therefore, for measuring and evaluating the effectiveness of the dissemination plan and the success of the project’s activities, the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) have been set:

Table 2: List of dissemination KPIs

Tools/Channels	Key Performance Indicator	Target value			
		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Total
Events	Project events: Participants	-	>70	>100	>100

	Conferences: Presentations (paper, session, workshop, poster)	>5	>10	>15	>30
	Trade shows: Exhibition stands and booths	>1	>1	>1	>3
	Webinars: Number organised/participants	1/50	2/50	2/50	5/50
Publications	Scientific publications (journal & conference proceedings): Number	>3	>5	>8	>16
	Trade magazines & Non-scientific publications: Number	>1	>2	>2	>5
Other	Videos: Number produced	>1	>2	>2	>5

KPIs related to the project’s communication activities, including website visitors, Twitter and LinkedIn quantitative indicators and technical leaflets are thoroughly described in D7.2 *Communication Strategy and Plan*.

3. Dissemination plan and activities

3.1. Demonstration events and final event

The project will organize 4 events, including **3 major demonstration events** at the three different Living Labs (LLs) to demonstrate the PoDIUM UCs in real traffic conditions, as well as the **final project event** helping to present the vision and strategy of CCAM partnership, and to efficiently showcase the project progress to multiple stakeholders.

Figure 1: Map of PoDIUM’s 3 Living Labs

3.1.1. Demonstrations at PoDIUM’s 3 Living Labs

The PoDIUM consortium has defined a rich set of 5 CCAM UCs (decomposed in many more individual Scenarios) with different connectivity and cooperation enablers and needs to be developed, integrated, evaluated, and demonstrated in real traffic conditions in 3 (2 of them dual; urban and

highway setup) well equipped and diversified LLs. PoDIUM’s demonstration events are an integral part of the project’s dissemination plan, aiming to multiply the impact of the project results on the different key audiences and encourage stakeholders to share their vision and common understanding of the project’s concept and approach. The main focus of the demo events is to unravel the work of PoDIUM partners in the respective 5 CCAM Use Cases (for additional information see D2.1 PoDIUM use cases description and specifications [3]), taking participants through the different stages of the development, integration, evaluation, and demonstration of solutions tested. PoDIUM will organize 3 major demonstration events in the following Living Labs:

- German Living Lab (see 3.1.1.1)
- Spanish Living Lab (see 3.1.1.2)
- Italian Living Lab (see 3.1.1.3)

Each demo event will be organized in collaboration with the respective LL leader and the involved partners. For enhanced impact and in order to facilitate the organisation of the LL demo events, determine the details and ensure optimum success, the WP7 team will prepare a list of requirements and a plan for dissemination activities to be shared with the LL leaders prior to the demo events. The list of responsibilities includes:

- a) the identification and invitation of relevant stakeholders;
- b) the issue of a press release (in English and local language);
- c) promotion activities through social media and online channels;
- d) complementary communication material in collaboration with T7.1 Leader.

3.1.1.1. German LL demonstration event

Table 3: German LL demonstration details

Living Lab	German
Expected date	TBD
Demo Site	Area of intersection of Mähringer Straße and Loherstraße in Ulm-Lehr, City of Ulm, Germany
Use Case 1	Cooperative Corridor Management in the City of Ulm
Workshop/Presentation Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cooperative infrastructure services for managing complex urban traffic situations in a local environment; - Development of reliability estimation mechanisms for trust-building in dynamic traffic information sources;
Target Groups	Public Authorities & Policy Makers, Automotive Industry Stakeholders & Associations, MNOs, Road Operators, Service Providers, RTOs, high level EU representatives, Innovation Ecosystems, Press
Partners Involved	UULM, BOSCH, NOKIA, UDE, City of Ulm (subcontractor to UULM)

3.1.1.2. Spanish LL demonstrations event

Table 4: Spanish LL demonstration details

Living Lab	Spanish
Expected Date	TBD

Demo sites	Barcelona urban LL (UC2) & Mediterranean (Spanish-France) CBC LL (UC3)
Use Case 2	PDI for a User-Centric, CCAM-enabled Traffic Management in Urban Corridors with High Priority Vehicles and VRUs
Workshop/Presentation Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Advanced/real-time traffic management strategies for the needs of VRUs and high priority vehicles; - Integration of CCAM to achieve EU safety and environmental targets.
Partners Involved	ETRA, IDIADA, MILLA, ISFM, RETE, BCN, IMI
Use Case 3	Responsive PDI enabling Vehicles and Road Users to Self-Manage in Real-time for Mixed Traffic Optimisation on the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor
Workshop/Presentation Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - On-demand sustainable multimodal transport service - Adoption of MaaS transportation systems for profitable, sustainable, and inclusive transport in cross-border areas and beyond.
Target Groups	Public Authorities & Policy Makers, Automotive Industry Stakeholders & Associations, MNOs, Road Operators, Service Providers, RTOs, high level EU representatives, Innovation Ecosystems, Press
Partners Involved	AAE, RETE, ENIDE, TENAL, IDIADA, i2CAT, UPC, MILLA, ISFM

3.1.1.3. Italian LL Demonstrations event

Table 5: Italian LL demonstration details

Living Lab	Italian
Expected Date	Q1 2025
Demo Sites	City of Turin (UC4) & Autostrada del Brennero - A22 Trento Highway Tunnel (UC5)
Use Case 4	Trusted Cooperative Perception for Intersection Manoeuvre Assistance
Workshop/Presentation Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The deployment of a close to market-ready PDI that implements a cooperative perception for CCAM services. - Demonstration of advanced cooperation strategies based on the information provided by the PDI.
Partners Involved	CRF, LINKS, SWM, SSC, TIM
Use Case 5	Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel
Workshop/Presentation Topics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Risk management in highway tunnels using sensors and information from vehicles with a full hybrid approach; - Deployment and validation of positioning technologies in tunnels to compute the absolute positioning of vehicles.
Target Groups	Public Authorities & Policy Makers, Automotive Industry Stakeholders & Associations, MNOs, Road Operators, Service Providers, RTOs, high level EU representatives, Innovation Ecosystems, Press
Partners Involved	BRE, CRF, LINKS, TIM

3.1.2. PoDIUM's final event

In the last year of the project, a PoDIUM Final Event will be hosted by one of the partners, attracting about 100 relevant stakeholders. During the event, the PoDIUM final findings and lessons learned will be presented. A press release will be issued prior to the event, while (local) media will be also invited to the event for a press conference and to experience first-hand the project results through demos, presentations, and interviews with consortium members. To secure wide post-event dissemination, the material i.e., the press release and the technical presentations will be made available through a dedicated page on the PoDIUM website, while a video will be created and promoted through every available channel.

3.2. Conferences, Events and Publications

3.2.1. Conferences and events

PoDIUM will both organise and participate in conferences, networking activities and events to promote project results to target stakeholders through personal interaction. Partners will participate in a number of industry events: conferences, congresses, workshops and other external events with the aim to disseminate the project's progress and its results, as well as to receive feedback from experts and relevant stakeholders. The consortium will also select fairs and exhibitions around Europe and globally to present the project's progress and also to address potential future customers (by participation in the booths of the consortium industrial partners). Such events can play an important role in community building, which is crucial for sustainability and development goals.

Special effort will be made for participating in annual **ITS World and EU Congresses** and **EUCNCs**, while other examples of targeted conferences include, but are not limited to IEEE INFOCOM, ACM Sigmetrics, IEEE International Conference on Communications (ICC), IEEE Global Communications Conference (GLOBECOM), IEEE International Symposium on a World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks (WoWMoM), IEEE Vehicular Technology Conference (VTC), IEEE Vehicular Networking Conference (VNC), IEEE International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC), IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), etc. Where possible, the project will capitalise on partners' or the EU's presence at international or regional events. Additional events will be further identified in the course of the project and partners will be kept informed about future opportunities for dissemination to properly plan their activities. For this reason, an online Calendar of Events has been created and shared with partners, which is regularly updated with events relevant to PoDIUM.

3.2.2. Journal publications and conference proceedings

PoDIUM will publish its activities and results in scientific peer-reviewed journals and in conference proceedings in order to broadcast its results and get feedback from the scientific and professional community. The consortium will also seek out publication channels in trade journals and magazines to bring our outcomes to end users. All scientific publications stemming from the project research will be made available through green or/and gold open access. Some examples of targeted journals are: IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, IEEE Open Journal of Intelligent Transport Systems, IEEE Communications Magazine, IEEE Transactions on Mobile Computing, IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications, Elsevier Computer Networks, Elsevier Compute Communications, etc.

3.2.3. Target dissemination opportunities and topics

Table 6 below presents a compilation of opportunities in leading conferences and events as well as scientific journals and technical magazines in the fields of telecommunications, transport & mobility, and 5G innovations. The selection was based on the individual plans collected by different partners and on other available opportunities that fulfill criteria in terms of focus areas and themes, location and place of activity, audience involvement, and overall reputation. In the course of the project, more suitable opportunities will arise and be seized.

Table 6: Partner Individual Dissemination Plans

Partner	Target Dissemination Opportunities and Topics
ICCS (Coordinator - RTO)	Conferences: ITS EU and World Congresses, EuCNC, IEEE GLOBECOM, IEEE INFOCOM etc.
	Journals & Magazines: IEEE Trans. on ITS, IEEE Open Journal of ITS, IEEE Comm. Magazine, IEEE Trans. on Mobile Computing etc.
	Topics and focus areas: Introduction to the project, its vision and its results with a focus on reliable communications as advanced an CCAM services enabler.
BOSCH (Tier-1 automotive supplier)	Conferences: ITS EU Congresses
	Topic: Description of German pilot and use cases focus area of Bosch
AAE (Road Operator)	Conferences: Congreso Español Sobre Sistemas Inteligentes de Transporte 2024/2025, TRA2024, ITS EU Congress 2025, ITS World Congress 2025, EUCAD 2025, RTR Conference 2025
	Topics and focus areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UC3: Responsive PDI enabling Vehicles and Road Users to Self-Manage in Real-time for Mixed Traffic Optimisation on the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor • Spanish Living Lab activities • Project Results
	Other Dissemination Activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organisation of the Demonstration event for UC3 • Presentations to National and EU associations and platforms, e.g. CCAM partnership, European Association of Operators of Toll Road Infrastructures (ASECAP), Conference of European Directors of Roads (CEDR), European Union Road Federation (ERF), Spanish Ministry of Transport, Mobility and Urban Agenda (MITMA), C-ROADS platform, ERTICO, International Road Transport Union (IRU), International Road Federation (IRF), etc.
ATE (RTO)	Conferences/Events: C-ROADS Workshops or similar events, ITS EU and World Congresses, joint dissemination activities with relevant project & initiatives
	Topics: C-ITS
BRE (Road and TMC operator)	Conferences: International Bridge, Tunnel and Turnpike Association (IBTTA) Technological Summit, ASECAP Days, IBTTA Annual Meetings, ITS EU and World Congresses
	Topics:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Brenner Motorway, first steps towards automated driving The Brenner Motorway as a living lab for testing on CCAM
CRF (OEM)	Conferences: ITS EU Congresses
	Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Presentation of the Italian LL with a focus on board system UC5: Risk Management in a Highway Tunnel technical aspects
	Other Dissemination Activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Co-organisation of Italian LL Demo Event; UC5 Technical Presentation at the PoDIUM Final Event
ENIDE (CAV application providers & SMEs)	Dissemination Activities: Enide will disseminate the project information with its stakeholders and networks, depending on the particular activity's target and objective.
ERTICO (CCAM-related partnership)	Conferences: ITS EU and World Congresses
	Dissemination Activities: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support with booth/exhibition organisation at the annual ITS Congresses Project promotion through regular articles in its newsroom and newsletter, which reaches more than 3500 recipients Promotion of project updates through ERTICO's social media channels (Twitter and LinkedIn)
ETRA (Road and TMC operator)	Conferences: Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC), IEEE ITSC, ITS EU Congress 2024/2025, TRA 2024
	Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Description of project activities progress and Barcelona Use Cases; Exploring the Benefits of Connected and Cooperative Mobility for Advanced Traffic Management; Improving Safety for Vulnerable Road Users Through Connected and Cooperative Mobility and V2X Communications; Ongoing project activities and results;
FSCOM (CAV application providers & SMEs)	N/A
I2CAT (RTO)	Conferences: International Conference on Transparent Optical Networks (ICTON) 2023, International Workshop on Computer and Networking Experimental Research using Testbeds (CNERT), organized in conjunction with INFOCOM 2023
	Journals: IEEE Access, etc.
	Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Awareness Information Dissemination using Aggregation into Collective Perception Messages for Connected Vehicles Advances in efficient distribution of V2X information over 5G Networks Demo: Interoperability between Cellular and V2X Networks (802.11p / LTE-PC5) under a Cloud Native Edge Scenario Wrap up of all results of efficient distribution of V2X information over 5G Networks

	<p>Other Dissemination Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with other partners in joint papers submitted to conferences or journals
<p>IDIADA (CCAM and road infrastructure industrial member)</p>	<p>Conferences: Mobile World Congress (MWC), Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC), ITSC 2023</p>
	<p>Topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of project activities progress and Barcelona Use Cases • V2X information over 5G Networks
	<p>Other Dissemination Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration with other partners in joint papers submitted to conferences or journals • IDIADA will make use of its social media channels (LinkedIn) to promote PoDIUM regularly, through own posts and retweets of the PoDIUM channels • IDIADA will also share on its website information related to the project, share press releases and/or blog articles if applies
<p>INCITES (CAV application providers & SMEs)</p>	<p>Conferences: European Conference on Networks and Communications (EuCNC), Conference of Telecommunication, Media and Internet Techno-Economics (CTTE), Infocom World, Infocom Mobile Connected World Greece, Arch Summit Luxembourg</p>
	<p>Journals: Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies (Wiley), Telematics and Informatics (Elsevier), IEEE Telecommunications Policy, IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management</p>
	<p>Topic: Business aspects of PoDIUM</p>
<p>LINKS (RTO)</p>	<p>Conferences: EUCNC 2024, International Conference on Cyber Resilience and Security (ICCRS) 2024</p>
	<p>Topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Autonomous driving and V2X solutions • Truthfulness/trustworthiness
<p>MILLA (OEM)</p>	N/A
<p>NOKIA (Telecom Vendor)</p>	Participation at events and publications.
<p>RETE (MNO)</p>	<p>Conferences: Mobile World Congresses</p>
	<p>Topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • UC2: Traffic management in urban corridors • UC3: Mixed Traffic Optimization on the Mediterranean Cross-Border Corridor
	<p>Other Dissemination Activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slides on a screen at Cellnex Booth, with general view of the project focusing on use cases • Video showcasing UC2 & UC3 • Short publications on LinkedIn and Twitter Cellnex profiles, highlighting important project events (press releases, UC demos, etc.) • Cellnex Trend articles to be used for branded articles on selected media

SWARCO (CCAM and road infrastructure industrial member)	Conferences & Events: ITS EU Congresses, SWARCO International Innovation workshop 2024
	Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of Italian pilot and use cases and activities carried out by SWARCO • Description of project activities progress and obtained results
TIM (MNO)	Events: TIM Innovation SAL, TIM internal workshop with business department
	Journals & Magazines: Notiziario Tecnico TIM
	Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Description of project activities progress and obtained results • Description of project activities carried out by TIM
UDE (RTO)	Conferences: IEEE ICC, IEEE Local Computer Networks (LCN), IEEE International Conference on Local and Metropolitan Area Networks (LANMAN), International Federation for Information Processing (IFIP) Networking, IEEE INFOCOM/USENIX Symposium on Networked Systems Design and Implementation (NSDI)
	Journals: IEEE Transactions on Network and Service Management (TNSM), Elsevier Computer Communications, Elsevier Computer Networks
	Topics: Communication reliability, scheduling and multipathing
UULM (RTO)	Conferences: IEEE IV, IEEE ITSC, International Conference on Information Fusion (FUSION), IEEE Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS), International Conference on Robotics and Automation (ICRA)
	Journals: IEEE Transactions on IV, IEEE Robotics and Automation Letters (RA-L), IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, IEEE Transaction on ITS, IEEE ITS Magazine
	Topics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperative connected and automated driving in urban traffic • Trust-building in information sources and processing modules/services
VICOM (RTO)	Conferences: ITS European Congress 2024, 2023 IEEE Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC 2023)
	Targeted Journals: IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems journal
IMI -BCN (Public Entity/ City Council)	Conferences: Smart City Expo World Congress (SCEWC)
	Topic: Description of project activities and results with a focus on the Spanish LL

3.3. PoDIUM webinars

Webinars addressing different topics and categories of stakeholders will be organised at regular intervals to provide a comprehensive view of particular results of the project. PoDIUM will organize at least 5 webinars in total. Three webinars are foreseen to take place in the first years and two more will be organised towards the end of the project (Table 7). It should be mentioned that this plan will be flexible regarding topics and timeline. Moreover, the proposed topics could either be replaced or postponed during the course of the project on its needs while more webinars might be added (if necessary).

Table 7: Webinar’s Plan

No.	Date	Description	Responsible Partner(s)
1.	~end of Year 1	Presentation of the PoDIUM common reference architecture platform, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Road-side ad-hoc and cellular communication infrastructure; • Cloud/edge computing infrastructure; • Road users (e.g., vehicles, VRUs with smart devices) and integrating the basic PoDIUM PDI functional components of perception models and digital twins, security trust models, and data truthfulness schemes. 	ETRA, BOSCH, ICCS
2.	M18 - M30	Description of the German LL and UCs: Challenges and preliminary results/lessons learned	UULM
3.	M18 - M30	Description of the Spanish LL and UCs: Challenges and preliminary results/lessons learned	AAE
4.	M18 - M30	Description of the Italian LL and UCs: Challenges and preliminary results/lessons learned	CRF
5.	M30-M36	Presentation of the results on the expected/potential public acceptance of the PoDIUM platform and the impact assessment of the PoDIUM solution.	ICCS, AAE, ETRA, CRF, BOSCH, UULM
6.	M30-M36	Exploring the sustainability of PoDIUM’s business model and its standardization impact.	INC, FSCOM

3.4. PoDIUM Videos

PoDIUM will produce 5 videos in total; 2 project-related videos and at least one video per Living Lab. The first project-related video will offer a short introduction to the project and its goals. Three more videos will be introducing the three Living Labs and the related Use Cases. The fifth and final video will be produced towards the end of the project (M36), summarizing the project’s outcomes and including a compilation of the project’s 5 Use Cases videos which will be produced during the three (public) demo events.

3.5. Liaison Activities and International Cooperation

Liaison Activities and International Cooperation is part of Task 7.3. This task will plan and execute PoDIUM liaison activities with related EU and international R&D initiatives, policy-makers, and related organisations and networks, to widely promote the project’s results. To maximise its impact, increase synergies, and avoid overlaps, PoDIUM will build on existing initiatives and projects in the EU in the field of CCAM and beyond. The PoDIUM consortium has already established strong links with all major initiatives, mainly through common partners. These initiatives include, among others, the European Automotive-Telecom Alliance ([EATA](#)), where PoDIUM partners BOSCH and TIM are key members, the [C-ROADS platform](#), the [SHOW](#) project, and the main 5G cross-border CCAM-related projects; [5G-CroCo](#), [5G-MOBIX](#), [5GMED](#), among others (see Table 8). Moreover, several experts of the consortium

are key members of the [CCAM](#) partnership, which will address technical, policy, and business challenges to promote the fast deployment of CCAM in Europe.

PoDIUM will create synergies with past and future R&D projects and liaison with already established networks, associations, organisations as well as related for a, and technical communities. Potential collaborations will be based on reciprocal benefits in terms of:

- Share information concerning each project approach, use cases, and goals;
- Exchange knowledge and views in common research fields;
- Present technical advances;
- Support activities to maximise the projects’ impact;
- Avoid overlapping.

The liaison activities may include joint activities, such as workshops, sessions, exhibitions, webinars or white papers. All liaison activities will mainly be communicated via the PoDIUM website and other channels such as through e-newsletter issues, social media, and so on.

The detailed planning of the liaison activities and international cooperation will take place only after T7.3 has started in M07 of the project, therefore there may be changes to what is written here.

Table 8: Overview of indicative PoDIUM related projects
(in bold with * the Project Coordinator)

Project/Initiative	Relevance to PoDIUM
Ongoing Projects	
5G-MED	5GMED will demonstrate advanced CCAM and FRMCS services along the “Barcelona – Perpignan” cross-border corridor, enabled by a multi-stakeholder compute and network infrastructure deployed by MNOs, neutral hosts, and road and rail operators, based on 5G Rel.16 and offering support for AI functions. Common PoDIUM partners: RETE (Cellnex)* , AAE, i2CAT End of Project: September 2023
5G-ROUTES	Advanced large-scale field tests of most representative CCAM applications to prove coherent performance across a key 5G cross-border corridor (Via Baltica). The results will increase confidence in 5G-based CCAM services and will accelerate their deployment. Common PoDIUM partners: ENIDE, SWM End of Project: September 2023
SHOW	Aims to support the migration path towards effective and sustainable urban transport through technical solutions, business models and priority scenarios for impact assessment. It deploys shared, connected, electrified fleets of autonomous vehicles in coordinated Public Transport (PT), Demand Responsive Transport (DRT), Mobility as a Service (MaaS) and Logistics as a Service (Laas) operational chains in more than 11 real-life urban demonstrations all across Europe. Common PoDIUM partners: ICCS, BOSCH, ATE, ERT, IDIADA, LINKS, SWM End of Project: December 2023

<p>5G-IANA</p>	<p>5G-IANA aims at providing an open 5G experimentation platform, on top of which third party experimenters (i.e., SMEs) in the Automotive-related 5G-PPP vertical will have the opportunity to develop, deploy and test their services. 5G-IANA will target different virtualization technologies integrating different MANO frameworks for enabling the deployment of the end-to-end network services across different domains (vehicles, road infrastructure, MEC nodes and cloud resources). 5G IANA will be demonstrated through 7 Automotive-related use cases in 2 5G SA testbeds.</p> <p>Common PoDIUM partners: *ICCS, NOKIA, UULM, LINKS, FSCOM, VICOM</p> <p>End of Project: November 2024</p>
<p>C-ROADS</p>	<p>The C-ROADS Platform is a joint initiative of European Member States and road operators for testing and implementing C-ITS services in light of cross-border harmonisation and interoperability.</p> <p>C-ROADS Austria: ATE is a key member of all activities in Austria.</p> <p>C-ROADS Germany: SWM in key member in various pilots in Germany.</p> <p>C-ROADS Italy: CRF, TIM are key implementing bodies of C-ROADS ITALY 2. BRE, CRF, TIM are key implementing bodies of C-ROADS ITALY.</p> <p>C-ROADS Spain: AAE in key implementing bodies in C-ROADS Spain.</p> <p>C-ROADS Greece: ICCS in beneficiaries list and co-coordinator of all activities</p>
<p>LUKAS</p>	<p>Assistance of L4 automated driving by communication object information from infrastructure sensors and connected road users via an environmental perception model on a MEC server in the LTE/5G mobile network to the automated vehicles and VRUs. Pilot site is in Ulm and the UC is coordinating VRUs, connected, and automated vehicles. Common PoDIUM partners: *BOSCH, NOKIA, UDE, UULM</p>
<p>Past Projects</p>	
<p>5G-MOBIX</p>	<p>Execution of connected, cooperative and autonomous mobility (CCAM) trials along Cross Border Corridors and urban sites using 5G core technological innovations to qualify the 5G infrastructure and evaluate its benefits in the CCAM context. Common PoDIUM partners: *ERTICO, ICCS, FSCOM, NOKIA, VICOM</p> <p>End of Project: September 2022</p>
<p>5G-CROCO</p>	<p>Project’s goal is to trial 5G technologies in the cross-border corridor connecting the cities of MetzMerzig-Luxembourg, traversing the borders between France, Germany and Luxembourg to validate advanced 5G features such as 5G New Radio, MEC-enabled distributed computing, Predictive QoS, Network Slicing, and improved positioning systems, all combined together, to enable innovative use cases for CCAM. Common PoDIUM partners: i2CAT, BOSCH, CRF, NOKIA</p> <p>End of Project: June 2022</p>
<p>ICT4CART</p>	<p>Hybrid communication approach where all the major wireless technologies, i.e. cellular and ITS G5, are integrated under a flexible “sliced” network architecture to enable the transition towards road transport automation.</p> <p>Common PoDIUM partners: *ICCS, BOSCH, ATE, CRF, ERT, NOKIA, UULM, LINKS, SWM</p> <p>End of Project: October 2021</p>

<p><u>C- MOBILE</u></p>	<p>Large-scale deployment of C-ITS services through hybrid communications in urban areas. Thanks to a common reference architecture 20 interoperable C-ITS services were deployed and assessed among nine European cities, involving 5.000+ users and more than 60 external stakeholders. To ease European adoption of such services and future ones, large scale deployment guidelines and procedures were defined, new business models were created, and a set of interoperability and standardisation recommendations was issued for future reference. A new urban mobility portal was launched containing these results and others, with the objective of providing key information to cities, regions and other organisations which want to deploy C-ITS services to improve mobility.</p> <p>Common PoDIUM partners: *IDIADA, BCN, ERT, SWM</p> <p>End of Project: November 2020</p>
<p><u>INFRAMIX</u></p>	<p>Prepare the road infrastructure with specific affordable adaptations and to support it with new models and tools, to accommodate for the step-wise introduction of automated vehicles.</p> <p>Common PoDIUM partners: *ATE, ICCS, AAE, ENIDE</p>

4. Conclusion

This deliverable outlines the activities that the PoDIUM consortium foresees to make for disseminating the project's outputs in the form of a plan which includes the topics, methods, tools, and channels that will be employed towards this goal. It is addressed to a wide audience consisting of PoDIUM partners, the European Commission, target groups, representatives of organizations involved in projects under similar topic, and anyone else interested.

Dissemination is an integral part of PoDIUM, as it is essential for the achievement of the project's mission and objectives. Therefore, the contribution of all partners is required ([Annex 4](#)). More specifically, all partners will be asked to support the implementation of the dissemination plan, by contributing to the development of the dissemination material, providing regular feedback, suggesting local contacts, providing translations, and all types of content requested by the task leader in order to ensure the effectiveness of the strategy. In addition, partners will be responsible and encouraged to attend events that are related to their expertise, keeping in mind the guidelines provided in this document, and to disseminate the material in their communications channels, for instance, websites, social media, newsletters, events, etc. Overall, the successfulness of the presented Dissemination Plan will be based on quantitative measurements compared with the set KPIs that will distinguish if corrective actions will be needed or not. The Dissemination Plan is considered as an adaptive live document and it will be further updated when needed according to the different project phases.

References

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Annexes

Annex 1 – Dissemination Procedure

Description and Purpose

The participation of any partner in an event, the publication or presentation of work done within the framework of PoDIUM or the performance of any other dissemination activity related to the project has to be approved beforehand by the PoDIUM Consortium.

The dissemination procedure is to be followed by all partners equally to:

- Produce high quality PoDIUM publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Efficiently monitor, record and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- Secure the brand identity of the project and the EC rules to be followed.

The WP7 leader (ERTICO) and the Task 7.2 leader (ICCS) are responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. **All partners are called to contribute efficiently on the dissemination of the project.**

Step by Step Procedure

Before any dissemination activity related to the PoDIUM project, the initiator of the activity should:

STEP 1: Notify the Task 7.2 Leader **at least 45 working days in advance**¹ about the intention to participate on a dissemination activity, sharing a) the details of the activity (date of event, name of journal, title of activity, audience, etc.), b) their specific role in it (presenter, organiser, speaker in a session, etc.) and c) a short description (up to 150 words) of the activity and how it is related to PoDIUM;

STEP 2: Register the activity in the applicable tab on the Dissemination Register, specifying all the details regarding the activity, as indicated in each column of the file;

STEP 3: If applicable, store the relevant material (abstract, draft paper, poster, article, presentation, press release etc.) in the WP7 Dissemination folder on Redmine, under the related sub-folder (Events, Publications or Other);

STEP 4: Task 7.2 leader has 2 days to react and send the request to the Consortium for approval, modification or rejection;

STEP 5: Any Consortium member may raise a modification or rejection request along with comments which should be sent to the Task 7.2 leader within 30 days; no response is considered as an approval;

STEP 6: The Task 7.2 leader informs the initiator of the dissemination activity and the Project Coordinator about the decision.

¹ PoDIUM Consortium Agreement, p.20

In case of:

- a) **Approval:** The initiator may proceed with the submission or realization of the planned dissemination activity;
- b) **Conflict/objection:** Any Consortium member can object to the proposed dissemination activity, for example in cases of risk of disclosure of restricted or confidential information. The objection has to include a clear reasoning as well as a precise request for necessary modifications that would make the dissemination acceptable.

The issue is discussed among the Coordinator, the Task 7.2 Leader and the involved partners.

Dissemination Activities report

Within **ten working days** after the realisation of the dissemination activity, the partner should provide the Task 7.2 Leader with the filled in dissemination report that is available on Redmine and the presented dissemination material (final paper, presentation, poster etc.). It will be also appreciated if the lead partner of every dissemination activity provides the WP7 Leader and Task 7.2 Leader with some photos of the participation at the event. The partners are requested to complete all the fields briefly and clearly, trying to avoid the use of abbreviations. The filled in report, as well as all the material received, will be archived by ICCS to the Dissemination Activity Inventory on Redmine.

Annex 2 – WP7 tasks and leaders

Table 9: WP7 Tasks and Leaders

Task & Leader	Task Descriptions
<p>Task 7.1: Communication strategy and tools</p> <p>Leader: ERTICO</p>	<p>Define the overall dissemination and communication strategy to be followed so as to efficiently promote PoDIUM and its results to the different target audiences. The Plan will incorporate the specific messages to be targeted at specific audiences, through appropriate channels, considering their needs and concerns and will serve as a guide for the consortium to effectively allocate time and resources and maximise project impact. The main communication tools will be also produced and high impact communication activities will be deployed so as to achieve wide awareness on PoDIUM objectives and results. The PoDIUM main activities/communication tools, are the following: development of the project’s brand identity, website and social media accounts, a communication kit to facilitate the information flow and promotion of the project to a wider audience and at events i.e., a flagship flyer, a regular e-newsletter, short videos, a set of PoDIUMroll-up banners and one professional video.</p>
<p>Task 7.2: Dissemination activities and events</p> <p>Leader: ICCS</p>	<p>Ensure that the PoDIUM results are systematically disseminated to the expert communities and to relevant stakeholders throughout the lifetime of the project and increase the reach and impact of the project. Organise the presentation of PoDIUM activities and results in conferences and other events, through special sessions, oral and poster presentations and workshops. Ensure the production and publication of scientific and technical papers from the PoDIUM experts in conference proceedings and top ranked peer-reviewed scientific and technology journals. Organise demonstration events and press conferences, for each PoDIUM demonstration activity and during some targeted international conferences and trade fairs.</p>
<p>Task 7.3: Liaison activities and international cooperation</p> <p>Leader: ATE</p>	<p>This task will plan and execute PoDIUM liaison activities with related EU and international R&D initiatives, policy makers and related organisations and networks, to widely promote project’s results. Creation of synergies with past and future R&D projects and liaison with already established networks, associations, organisations as well as related fora and technical communities. Hereby especially the regular exchange and coordination with the project funded in the same call, but in area A is relevant for further development of the CCAM aspects in the EU. Coordinate with other relevant actors from the ongoing 5G-PPP projects.</p>
<p>Task 7.4: Exploitation strategy and IPR management</p> <p>Leader: ENIDE - TENAL</p>	<p>This task will define the necessary methodology, metrics and templates for the preparation of homogeneous and effective exploitation plans of PoDIUM. It will also outline specific business metrics for analysing the exploitation potential of the partners’ ideas, to define legal rights and obligations in the exploitation process, to set the precise procedure to be followed in order to define and agree upon IP Rights of each partner and to include templates and procedures to be followed in order to elaborate</p>

	the individual exploitation plans, which will be prepared by each of the participants on a regular yearly basis.
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Annex 3 – WP7 Deliverables

Table 10: WP7 List of Deliverables

No.	Title	Lead	Type	Dis. Level	Due date (in months)
D7.1	Brand identity and guidelines	ERTICO	DEC	Public	3
D7.2	Communication strategy and plan -V1	ERTICO	Report	Public	6
D7.3	Communications Tools – V1	ERTICO	DEC	Public	6
D7.4	Dissemination Plan	ICCS	Report	Public	6
D7.5	Communication strategy and plan V2	ERTICO	Report	Public	18
D7.6	Communication tools – V2	ERTICO	DEC	Public	18
D7.7	Exploitation plan -V1	ENIDE	Report	SEN	6
D7.8	Exploitation plan – V2	ENIDE	Report	SEN	18
D7.9	Report on the dissemination activities	ICCS	Report	Public	36
D7.10	Report on liaison activities and international cooperation	ATE	Report	Public	36
D7.11	Exploitation Report	ENIDE	Report	SEN	36

Annex 4 – WP7 participation per partner

All consortium members will participate in the activities of WP7 and the dissemination of PoDIUM results. ERTICO, WP7 Leader, is also the leader of Task 7.1 Communication strategy and tools. ICCS will lead Task 7.2, Dissemination activities and events and support with organization of the demonstration and final events. ATE leads Task 7.3 Liaison activities and international cooperation while ENIDE - TENAL leads Task 7.4 Exploitation strategy; all of them will have a major role in all WP7 activities. Allocated effort per partner is described in the below:

Table 11: Staff effort per partner

Partner	WP7 Effort
ICCS	16.50
BOSCH	2.00
AAE	0.50
ATE	4.00
BRE	1.00
CRF	6.00
ENIDE	4.00
TENAL	15.00
ERTICO	11.50
ETRA	2.00
FSCOM	6.00
I2CAT	0.50
IDIADA	1.00
INCITES	5.00
LINKS	3.00
MILLA	1.00
NOKIA	1.00
RETE	8.00
SWARCO	3.00
TIM	1.00
UDE	1.00
UULM	2.00
VICOM	5.00
BCN	1.00
IMI	3.00

